

Horizon 2020

1. Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Calculating Excess Returns and for plotting a histogram of excess returns

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Calculating Excess Returns and for plotting a histogram of excess returns

Dataset Assets: Calculating Excess Returns and for plotting a histogram of excess returns

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: CSV

Dataset Risk Free Rate: CSV

Dataset Assets: XLSX

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Re-used

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Re-used

Dataset Assets:

What is the origin of the data?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: coinmetrics.io

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Federal Reserve

Dataset Assets:

What is the expected size of the data?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Yes Handle / DOI

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Yes Handle / DOI

Dataset Assets: Yes Handle / DOI

What naming conventions do you follow?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: No

Dataset Risk Free Rate: No

Dataset Assets: No

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

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Do you provide clear version numbers?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: the datasets are downloaded. Therefore, no versioning is needed.

Dataset Risk Free Rate: the datasets are downloaded. Therefore, no versioning is needed.

Dataset Assets: the datasets are downloaded. Therefore, no versioning is needed.

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

Dataset Assets:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain data sets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Assets: Yes, externally for everyone

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Other: Github

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Other: Github

Dataset Assets: Other: Github

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: CSV

Dataset Risk Free Rate: CSV

Dataset Assets: XLSX

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Yes, externally for everyone

Dataset Assets: Yes, externally for everyone

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Other: Github (not certified)

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Other: Github (not certified)

Dataset Assets: Other: Github (not certified)

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: No

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

Is there a need for a data access committee?

No

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine-readable license)?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Everyone is allowed to access the dataset.

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Everyone is allowed to access the dataset.

Dataset Assets: Everyone is allowed to access the dataset.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Data Backups provided by the project team. There is no sensitive data.

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Data Backups provided by the project team. there is no sensitive data.

Dataset Assets: Data Backups provided by the project team. there is no sensitive data.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: Yes
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: Yes
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: Yes

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: Yes
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: Yes
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: Yes

Dataset Assets:

- The dataset adheres to standardised formats: Yes
- The dataset is usable with available (open) software applications or software applications that are established and widely used in the respective community: Yes
- The dataset can easily be re-combined with different datasets from different origins: Yes

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Public domain (CC0)

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Public domain (CC0)

Dataset Assets: Public domain (CC0)

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

Dataset Assets:

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: at least 1 year.

Dataset Risk Free Rate: at least 1 year.

Dataset Assets: at least 1 year.

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

Personnel: 0 PM

Other: 0 Euro

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

Preservation decisions

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Costs

Personnel: 0 PM

Other: 0 Euro

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: Other: Github (certified)

Dataset Risk Free Rate: Other: Github (not certified)

Dataset Assets: Other: Github (not certified)

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC: No

Dataset Risk Free Rate: No

Dataset Assets: No

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Dataset Adjusted Dayli Close Prices for LTC:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

Dataset Risk Free Rate:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

Dataset Assets:

- Personal data: No
- Informed consent:

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

Yes

We have to write a DMP for a lecture